

Infra-Red Spectra of Soils

SHARAFAT ALI, O. P. SINGH and S. K. DE

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211002 (India)

Manuscript received 25 October 1975; revised 3 May 1976; accepted 30 December 1976

Fifty representative soil samples collected from semi-desert, arid, semi-arid, semi-humid, humid-temperate and per-humid soil-climatic regions of India were processed for taking their infrared curves by KBr-mull technique using Perkin-Elmer Infra-Red Spectrophotometer, model no. 137. The infrared curves of each soil sample have been studied in the wavelength region, 2.5μ to 15.0μ . Previously, Functional groups, Si-OH (bonded and unbonded water-peaks); Si-OH (absorbed water-peak); Si-O (silica-peak); Al-O (alumina-peak); Si-H (pH-peak) and Si-C (carbon complex-peak) were assigned to this wavelength region. The common characteristic peaks of the functional group observed in the I.R. curves of soils belonging to different soil-climatic regions were noted. The total number of peaks, total number of strong, medium and weak peaks and distribution of these peaks in different infrared regions of IR-curves between wavelengths 2.70μ to 8.0μ , 8.5μ to 10.3μ and 11.0μ to 15.0μ were also observed and discussed.

ULTRAVIOLET, infrared, nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy are important instrumental techniques that the chemists now use to gain information about the purity of a substance. Of these three, infrared spectroscopy appears to be more popular now-a-days especially in the fields of organic and physical chemistry where this technique has been widely applied between 2.5μ to 25μ both from the qualitative and quantitative points of view¹. However, in the branch of soil and clay chemistry its application has not been generally attempted.

De^{2,3} was the first to attempt the interpretations of IR-curves of soils taken as a whole in terms of their constituents and properties. It has been concluded from his findings that if the soil samples are taken under certain specific conditions and their IR-curves were taken only by KBr-mull technique⁴ under moisture free conditions, the resultant curve so obtained would speak well in terms of soil properties. Lal⁵ and Singh⁶ also worked in this line with a few U.P. soils who emphasized that this aspect of study still required further approach, so that this branch of science may pave the way for future analytical scientists where the time is the main factor. Since the IR-curves of soils collected from different parts of India and their interpretations as a whole are not available from the point of view of soil climatic regions the need of the present work is felt. In the present paper, therefore, the IR-study of fifty representative soil samples belonging to different soil climatic regions of India has been attempted by KBr-mull technique and the results on IR-peaks obtained have been interpreted in terms of several common soil properties in order to see their utility in the field of practical soil science.

Experimental

Fifty (50) representative soil samples belonging to semi-desert, arid, semi-arid, sub-humid, humid-temperate

and per-humid soil-climatic⁷ regions of India have been collected from a depth of 0-15 cm. These soils were dried in air, separated from visible organic matters, pulverised in an agate-mortar and then passed through 100-mesh (British Standard) sieve. These soils were then chemically analysed⁸ for their different physico-chemical properties (Table 1).

The infrared curves of fifty Indian soils were obtained by KBr-mull technique through Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer model no. 137⁸. The KBr-mull technique for obtaining the IR-curves of the soil samples was used due to the fact that KBr does not absorb the infrared light in the region between 2.5μ to 15.0μ (our range of study) and therefore a complete spectrum of the soil sample is obtained.

The infrared curves of each soil sample have been studied in the wavelength 2.5μ to 15.0μ to which particular functional groups for Si-OH (bonded and unbonded water-peaks, A); Si-OH (absorbed water-peak, B); Si-O (silica-peak, C); Al-O (alumina-peak, D); Si-H (PH-peak, E) and Si-C (carbon-peak, F) infrared regions have been allocated³. Each of these functional groups mentioned above has been given in Table-2.

Results and Discussion

A perusal of Table-2 clearly shows the distribution of infrared peaks in different infrared regions viz., Si-OH (A, 2.70μ to 3.50μ), Si-OH (B, 4.20 - 8.00μ), Si-O (C, 8.50 - 9.50μ), Al-O (D, 9.50 - 10.30μ), Si-H (E, 10.95 - 11.30μ) and Si-C (F, 12.0 - 15.0μ) of IR-curves of fifty representative soils belonging to semi-desert, arid, semi-arid, sub-humid, humid and perhumid soil-climatic regions of India. The IR-curves of fifty soils belonging to different soil-climatic regions have been avoided to economise space but one comparative table (Table 2) is being given to show the different characteristic peaks in different regions of IR-curves.

TABLE 1—SOME PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF SOILS BELONGING TO DIFFERENT SOIL-CLIMATIC-REGIONS

Soil	Soil Properties					pH	Texture
	SiO ₂ %	R ₂ O ₃ %	Al ₂ O ₃ %	C/N	B. E. C. meq. %.		
(i) Jodhpur, (Rajasthan)	93.60	5.72	4.60	7.71	14.95	8.40	Sandy clay loam
Agra, U. P.	88.0	8.71	4.77	18.50	15.15	8.80	Loamy sand
Aligarh, U. P.	91.93	5.27	2.91	16.50	13.50	9.0	Sandy loam
(ii) Allahabad, U. P.	90.20	7.51	4.60	5.56	18.95	7.40	Sandy clay loam
Mehsana, Gujrat	92.88	5.53	3.98	9.50	17.50	8.70	Sandy loam.
Farrukhabad, U. P.	81.80	14.18	9.80	9.60	19.30	7.50	Sandy clay loam
Fatehpur U. P.	86.23	9.05	5.53	19.80	17.68	8.50	—do—
Indore, M. P.	70.40	25.21	18.53	7.75	21.50	8.10	Sandy clay loam
Shivapuri „	89.47	5.93	3.45	12.0	16.25	7.30	Sandy clay loam
Nander, Maharashtra	64.48	30.32	25.20	7.49	20.60	8.70	—do—
Parbhani „	63.16	22.86	19.34	5.90	23.0	8.70	—do—
Poona „	60.28	34.71	29.51	10.37	22.50	6.40	—do—
Jalgaon „	67.94	21.22	17.02	6.55	24.80	8.40	—do—
Nasik „	84.25	20.07	18.75	6.38	14.50	7.20	—do—
Dhulia „	79.54	14.95	9.51	10.25	17.00	8.30	—do—
Darapuram, T. N.	85.20	11.00	7.0	8.58	19.56	7.50	Sandy loam
Godavari, A. P.	95.41	4.15	2.35	7.30	20.17	6.20	Sandy clay loam
Guntur „	74.28	10.57	8.25	3.23	22.50	8.80	—do—
Bangalore, Karnatak	86.14	12.81	9.57	19.29	20.80	6.30	—do—
Mandeya „	83.65	11.65	10.79	9.40	18.20	6.80	Sandy clay loam
(iii) Azamgarh, U. P.	90.20	6.90	3.84	14.66	20.95	7.80	Sandy clay loam
Lakhimpur Kheri U. P.	87.80	9.40	5.50	4.33	18.90	7.30	Sandy loam
Varanasi U. P.	86.20	10.44	7.80	13.0	19.50	9.10	Loamy sand
Jaunpur „	89.40	9.10	8.56	33.0	10.64	8.50	Sandy loam
Ghazipur „	90.68	5.60	3.15	9.10	22.45	7.40	—do—
Bareilly „	60.58	13.30	5.95	7.10	32.56	8.60	Loamy sand
Banda „	92.20	5.57	2.7	17.0	13.60	7.80	Sandy loam
Jhansi „	84.35	8.59	5.87	6.80	10.50	6.30	—do—
Mirzapur „	82.60	12.20	9.20	4.25	23.40	6.80	Loamy sand
Dhanbad, Bihar	95.40	4.36	3.06	4.23	34.56	6.80	Loam
Burdwan, W. B.	85.62	9.0	7.33	8.0	17.76	6.30	Sandy clay loam
Koraput, Orissa	70.22	7.62	5.07	24.83	30.30	7.80	Loam
Gora	67.32	27.22	18.78	15.66	15.80	8.90	Sandy clay loam
Sultanpur, U. P.	89.20	7.25	5.09				Sandy loam
(iv) Dehradun, U. P.	90.80	5.60	8.80	7.88	15.25	7.10	—do—
Nainital, U. P.	84.60	13.36	10.18	9.80	9.84	8.80	—do—
Gorakhpur „	91.00	6.28	4.08	9.50	11.60	7.20	—do—
Calcutta, W. B.	85.62	9.0	7.33	12.97	9.51	7.50	Clay loam
Sibsagar, Assam	85.82	11.93	8.73	14.13	13.50	8.30	Sandy clay loam
Nongaon, „	90.16	7.71	5.71	8.60	6.25	8.40	Sandy clay loam
Chauba, H. P.	82.94	13.36	12.06	15.70	7.20	7.70	—do—
Ranchi, Bihar	85.60	11.96	9.30	9.28	8.20	6.40	Sandy loam
(v) Almorah, U. P.	88.0	9.72	7.0	11.10	15.60	6.20	—do—
Mussorie, U. P.	90.62	5.60	8.60	29.80	9.84	7.90	Sandy clay loam
Ratnagiri, Maharashtra	65.10	42.0	39.84	5.24	23.0	5.70	—do—
Nilgiris, T. N.	72.28	15.03	11.10	9.23	20.20	5.50	—do—
Lakhimpur, Assam	89.68	13.36	10.52	6.42	12.50	6.60	—do—
Kerala	78.02	18.0	12.32	8.57	29.56	6.70	Sandy clay loam
(vi) Palampur, H. P.	79.30	20.95	18.15	8.0	16.75	6.00	—do—
Darjeeling, W. B.	82.85	16.72	13.92	7.85	18.80	5.20	

Note : (i)=Semi-desert, (ii)=Arid, (iii)=Semi-arid,
 (iv)=Sub-humid (v)=Humid-temperate, and
 (vi)=Per-humid-Soil climatic regions.

TABLE-2—INFRARED ABSORPTION PEAKS OF SOILS BELONGING TO DIFFERENT SOIL-CLIMATIC REGIONS

Soil Climatic region.	WAVE LENGTHS (μ)					
	FUNCTIONAL GROUPS		FUNCTIONAL GROUPS			
1	Si-OH (Bonded and un-Bonded water-peaks) 2.70-3.50 (A)	Si-OH (Absorbed water-peak) 4.20-8.00 (B)	Si-O (Silica-peak) 8.50-9.50 (C)	Al-O (Alumina peak) 9.50-10.30 (D)	Si-H (pH-peak) 10.95-11.30 (E)	Si-C (Carbon-peak) 12.00-15.00 (F)
2	3	4	5	6	7	
<i>Semi-desert</i>						
Jodhpur	2.50(M), 3.05(M)	4.35(M), 6.15(M) 6.90(M)	9.10(M)	9.75(S)	11.0(M)	12.50(M), 13.50(M) 14.30(M)
Agra	2.80(M), 2.0(M)	4.35(M), 6.15(M) 6.90(M)	9.10(M)	9.75(S)	11.0(M)	12.5 (M), 13.50(M) 14.30(M)
Aligarh	3.10(M)	4.35(M), 6.15(M) 6.90(M)	9.10(M)	9.75(S)	11.0(M)	12.50(M), 13.10(M) 13.90(M), 14.35(M)
<i>Arid</i>						
Allahabad	2.80(M), 3.0(M), 3.45(M)	4.25(M), 6.10(M)	—	9.70(S), 10.0(S)	11.0(M)	12.5 (M), 14.40(M)
Mehsana	2.80(M), 3.0(M)	4.35(M), 5.40(M), 6.10(M)	—	9.70(S), 10.0(S)	11.0(M)	12.50(M), 14.40(M)
Farrukhabad	2.80(M), 2.90(M), 3.0 (M)	4.30(M), 6.10(M)	9.0 (S)	9.70(S), 10.0(S)	11.0(M)	12.50(M), 14.40(M)
Fatehpur	2.80(M), 3.0(M)	4.30(M), 6.10(M) 7.0(M)	9.10(S)	9.70(S), 10.0(S)	11.0(M)	12.50(M), 14.40(M)
Indore	2.80(M), 3.0(M)	4.30(M), 6.10(M)	9.10(S)	9.70(S)	10.95(M), 11.45(M)	12.50(M), 14.40(M)
Shivapuri	2.80(M), 3.0(M)	4.30(M), 6.10(M)	—	9.70(S), 10.0(S)	10.95(M), 11.20(M)	12.50(M), 14.40(M)
Nandar Parbhani	2.80(M), 3.0(M) 2.80(M), 3.0(M)	4.30(M), 6.10(M) 4.30(M), 6.10(M)	— 9.0 (S)	9.70(S), 10.0(S) 9.70(S)	10.95(M), 11.45*(M) 10.95(M), 11.40**(M)	12.50(M), 14.40(M) 12.50(M), 14.40(M)
Poona	2.80(M), 3.0(M)	4.30(M), 6.10(M)	9.0 (M)	9.70(S), 9.85(S)	10.95(M)	12.50(M), 14.40(M)
Jalgaon	2.80(M), 3.0(M)	4.30(M), 6.10(M)	—	9.70(S), 9.95(S)	10.95(M), 11.40*(M)	12.50(M), 14.40(M)
Nasik	2.80(M), 3.0(M)	4.30(M), 6.10(M)	9.10(M)	9.70(S)	10.95(M), 11.50*(M)	12.50(M), 14.40(M)
Dhulia	2.80(M), 3.0(M)	4.35(M), 6.10(M)	9.10(S)	9.70(S)	11.0(M), 11.50**(M)	12.50(M), 14.40(M)
Dharapuram	2.80(M), 3.0(M)	4.30(M), 6.10(M) 6.30(M)	9.0(M)	9.70(S)	10.95(M)	12.50(M), 14.40(M)
Godawari Guntur	2.80(M), 3.0(M) 2.80(M), 3.0(M)	4.25(M), 6.10(M) 4.30(M), 6.10(M)	9.10(S) —	9.70(S), 9.90(S) 9.70(S)	10.95(M) 10.95(M), 11.45*(M)	12.50(M), 14.40(M) 12.50(M), 14.40(M)
Bangalore Mandeya	2.80(M), 3.0(M) 2.80(M), 3.0(M)	4.30(M), 6.10(M) 4.30(M), 6.10(M)	9.10(M) 9.0 (M)	9.70(S), 9.95(S) 9.70(S)	10.95(M) 10.95(S)	12.50(M), 14.40(M) 12.50(M), 14.40(M)
<i>Semi-arid</i>						
Azamgarh	2.75(M), 2.95(M) 3.45(M)	4.30(M), 6.10(M) 7.30(M)	9.1 (M)	9.75(S)	11.0 (M)	12.50(M), 14.40(M)
Lakhimpur-kheri.	2.75(M), 2.95(M) 3.45(M)	4.30(M), 6.10(M)	9.10(M)	9.75(S)	11.10(M)	12.50(M), 14.40(M)
Varanasi	2.75(M), 2.95(M) 3.45(M)	4.30(M), 6.10(M)	9.10(M)	9.75(M)	11.0 (M)	12.50(M), 14.40(M)
Jaunpur	2.95(M), 3.10(M) 3.45(M)	4.30(M), 6.10(M)	9.10(M)	9.75(S)	11.0 (M)	12.50(M), 12.95(M) 14.40(M)
Ghazipur	2.75(M), 2.95(M) 3.30(M)	4.30(M), 6.10(M)	9.10(M)	9.75(S)	11.0 (M)	12.50(M), 12.95(M) 14.40(M)
Bareilly	2.95(M), 3.0(M)	4.35(M), 6.10(M)	9.10(S)	9.75(S)	10.95(M), 11.40*(M)	12.50(M), 13.50(M) 14.40(M)
Banda	2.75(M), 2.95(M) 3.50(M)	4.30(M), 6.10(M)	9.10(S)	9.75(S)	11.0 (M), 12.50(M)	12.85(M), 14.40(M)
Jhansi	2.75(M), 2.95(M) 3.10(M)	4.30(M), 4.40(M) 5.75(M), 6.10(M)	9.10(S)	9.75(S)	11.0 (M), 12.50(M)	12.80(M), 14.40(M)
Mirzapur Dhanbad	2.90(M), 3.0 (M) 2.95(M), 3.10(M)	4.30(M), 6.10(M) 4.30(M), 6.10(M)	9.10(M) 9.10(M)	9.75(S) 9.75(S)	10.95(M), 12.50(M) 10.95(M), 12.50(M)	12.85(M), 14.40(M) 13.20(M), 14.40(M)
Burdwan	2.80(M), 2.95(M) 3.10(M)	4.30(W), 6.10(W)	9.10(M)	9.75(S)	10.95(M), 12.50(M)	12.80(M), 14.40(M)
Koraput	2.80(M), 2.95(M) 3.50(M)	4.30(M), 6.10(M) 6.40(M)	8.95(S)	9.75(S)	10.95(M), 12.50(M)	14.40(M)
Gova Sultanpur	2.95(M), 3.45(M) 2.75(M), 2.95(M) 3.50(M)	4.30(M), 6.10(M)	9.10(M) 9.10(M)	9.75(S) 9.75(S) 10.50(M)*	10.95(M), 12.50(M) 11.0 (M), 12.50(M)	14.40(M) 14.40(M)

(Contd. Table 2)

(Contd. Table 2)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
<i>Sub-humid</i>						
Denradun	2.80(M), 3.50(M)	4.35(M), 6.15(M), 8.0(M)	9.10(M)	9.70(S)	11.0(M), 12.50(M)	14.45(M)
Nainital	2.0(M), 3.0(M) 3.50(M)	4.30(M), 6.15(M) 7.05(M)	8.50(M) 9.0(M)	9.70(S)	11.0(M), 12.50(M)	12.0(M), 14.45(M)
Gorakhpur	2.80(M), 3.0(M) 3.50(M)	4.35(M), 6.15(M)	8.50(M) 9.0(S)	9.80(S)	11.0(M), 12.50(M)	14.45(M)
Calcutta	2.80(M), 3.50(M)	4.35(M), 6.15(M)	8.50(M)	9.80(S)	11.0(M), 12.50(M)	14.45(M)
Sibsagar	2.80(M), 3.50(M)	4.30(M), 6.15(M)	9.0(M)	9.70(M)	11.0(M), 12.6(M)	12.80(M), 14.45(M)
Nawgaon	2.80(M), 3.0(M) 3.50(M)	4.35(M), 6.15(M) 7.10(M)	8.50(M) 9.0(M)	9.70(M)	11.0(M), 12.50(M)	12.80(M), 14.45(M)
Chamba	2.80(M), 3.50(M)	4.35(M), 6.15(M) 8.0(M)	8.50(M) 9.0(M)	9.80(S)	11.0(M), 12.50(M)	14.45(M)
Ranchi	2.80(M), 3.50(M)	4.35(M), 6.15(M) 8.0(M)	9.0(M) 9.0(S)	9.70(S)	11.0(M), 12.50(M)	14.45(M)
<i>Humid</i>						
Almorah	2.75(M), 2.95(M)	4.25(M), 6.20(M) 7.60(M)	9.10(S)	9.95(S)	11.00(M)	12.50(M), 13.10(M) 13.35(M), 14.45(M)
Mussorie	2.95(M), 3.10(M)	4.25(M), 6.20(M) 6.90(M), 7.40(M)	9.10(M)	9.95(S)	11.00(M)	12.50(M), 13.10(M) 14.45(M)
Ratnagiri	2.75(M), 2.95(M)	4.30(M), 6.20(W) 7.40(W)	9.10(S)	9.70(S), 9.95(S)	10.95(M)	12.54(M), 13.35(M) 14.45(M)
Nilgiris	2.80(M), 2.25(M) 3.10(M)	4.35(M), 6.25(M)	—	9.70(S)	11.0(M), 11.4*(M)	12.50(M), 13.35(M) 14.45(M)
Lakhimpur	2.95(M)	4.30(W), 5.25(W) 6.10(M), 6.65(M)	9.10(S)	9.70(S)	11.0(M)	12.00(M), 13.10(M) 14.45(M)
Kerala	2.75(M), 2.95(M)	4.30(M), 6.10(M)	9.10(M)	9.70(S)	10.95(M), 11.4*(M)	12.50(M), 13.10(M) 14.45(M)
<i>Per-humid</i>						
Palampur	2.75(M), 2.95(M) 3.45(M)	4.30(M), 6.15(M) 7.35(M), 8.10(M)	9.10(S)	9.75(S), 10.0(S)	10.95(M)	12.50(M), 13.35(M) 14.45(M)
Darjeeling	2.80(M), 3.0(M) 3.50(M)	4.35(M), 6.15(M) 7.35(M), 8.10(M)	9.10(S)	9.75(S), 10.0(S)	10.95(M)	12.50(M), 13.35(M) 14.45(M)

Note : 1. S= Strong (Transmittance below 25%),

M= Medium (Transmittance between 25 to 75%) and

W=Weak (Transmittance above 75%).

2. (,) =The figures are not yet been allotted.

It may be seen (Table 2) that there are some common peak values in all the three soils (*viz.*, Jodhpur, Agra, Aligarh soils) of semi-desert-climatic regions, *viz.* 4.35 μ , 6.10 μ , 6.90 μ , 9.10 μ , 9.75 μ , 11.0 μ , 12.50 μ and 13.50 μ (Jodhpur and Agra soils only). These may well be utilized for the identification of these soils. This would mean that under semi-desert regions, the functional group associated with these peak values would exhibit similarity in such soil properties as are associated with them. Thus, the inconspicuous nature of the peak at 11.0 μ which is assigned to Si-H bond (E) and is stated to speak about the nature of pH, indicates, that all the three soils *viz.*, Jodhpur (sandy-loam), Agra & Aligarh (Sandy clay loam) have almost the same scale of pH values (Table 1). It may be seen that all these soils have pH value in the alkaline range and their pH measures generally do not vary much. It may be further observed (Table 3) that all the three soils of semi-desert region have 11 total number of peaks,

although there is slight variation in the total number of strong peaks and this variation is not much in the distribution of total peaks in different IR-regions of the soils (Table 3). The strong (S) peaks in case of all the three soils are found in Al-O (D) functional groups at the wavelength of 9.75 μ (Table 2). According to De², the strength of the peak depends upon the perfectness of the bond of the constituting atoms of the functional group. Since the climate prevalent in the semi-desert region is characterised by tremendous heat variation with very little moisture or precipitation, the chances of formation of perfect functional groups in different infrared active soil constituents would obviously be small. Under such conditions, it is quite likely that the number of strong(S) as well as the weak(W) peaks under this region would be very few in number. This may be actually seen in Table 1 where it has been observed that the medium (M) peaks are much higher in number than either the strong or weak peaks.

TABLE 3—TOTAL NUMBER OF PEAKS IN IR—CURVES OF SOILS BELONGING TO DIFFERENT SOIL CLIMATIC REGIONS.

Soil-climatic region	Total number of peaks	Total number of strong peaks	Distribution of total peaks in different region of IR-curves (μ)		
			2.70—8.00	8.50—10.30	11.00—15.00
<i>Semi-Desert</i>					
Jodhpur	11	1	5	2	4
Agra	11	—	5	2	4
Aligarh	11	2	4	2	5
<i>Arid</i>					
Allahabad	10	2	5	2	3
Mehsana	10	1	5	2	3
Farrukhabad	11	3	5	3	3
Fatehpur	11	3	5	3	3
Indore	10	2	4	3	3
Shivapuri	10	2	4	2	4
Nander	10	2	4	2	4
Parbhani	11	2	5	2	4
Poona	10	2	4	3	3
Jalgaon	10	2	4	2	4
Nasik	10	1	4	2	4
Dhulia	10	2	4	2	4
Dharapuram	10	1	5	2	3
Godavari	10	3	4	3	4
Guntur	10	1	5	2	4
Bangalore	10	2	4	2	4
Mandeya	10	1	5	2	3
<i>Semi-arid</i>					
Azamgarh	11	1	6	2	3
Lakhimpur Kheri	10	1	5	2	3
Varanasi	11	—	5	3	3
Jaunpur	11	3	5	2	4
Ghazipur	11	1	5	2	4
Bareilly	10	2	4	2	4
Banda	11	2	5	2	4
Jhansi	14	2	8	2	4
Mirzapur	10	2	4	2	4
Sultanpur	11	1	5	3	3
Dhanbad	10	1	4	2	4
Burdwan	11	1	5	2	4
Koraput	13	3	7	3	4
Gova	10	1	4	2	4
<i>Sub-humid</i>					
Dehradun	10	1	5	2	3
Nainital	13	1	6	3	4
Gorakhpur	11	2	5	2	4
Calcutta	10	1	4	3	3
Sibsagar	11	—	4	3	4
Newgaon	13	1	6	3	4
Chamba	10	1	5	2	3
Ranchi	10	2	5	2	3
<i>Humid-temperate</i>					
Almorah	11	2	5	2	4
Mussorie	12	1	6	2	4
Ratnagiri	12	3	5	3	4
Nilgiri	11	1	5	1	5
Lakhimpur	11	3	4	3	4
Kerala	11	1	4	2	5
<i>Per-Humid</i>					
Palampur	14	3	7	3	4
Darjeeling	14	3	7	4	3

The arid region which comprises of 17 different soils clearly indicates (Table 2) that the common peak values for all the arid soils are 2.80μ , 3.0μ , 8.10μ , 9.70μ ,

12.50μ and 14.40μ distributed in different infrared regions of IR-curves of soils. The other peak values are present only in limited number of soils and therefore these peak values may be said to be important for the particular soils in which these have been found. Incidentally it may be said here that De^2 pointed out that for Si-H (E) functional group the IR-absorption peak generally appears between 11.0μ to 11.20μ but in our case however, it has been found that for this particular infrared region the 12 soils record the peak value at 10.95μ (Table 2). The characteristic peak values in this functional group clearly show the variation in pH values of all the arid soils (Table 1) depending upon the size and depth of these peaks in IR-curves of soils. The total number of peaks as shown in table 3 in arid-region are found to be generally 10 in all the arid soils except three soils (viz., Farrukhabad, Fatehpur, Parbhani soils) which record the total number of peaks equal to 11. This slight variation in total number of IR-peaks to be due to the total number of strong peaks (varies from 1 to 3) and the total peaks appearing between 8.50μ to 10.30μ of the IR-curves. The peaks between 2.70μ to 8.0μ and 11.0μ to 15.0μ are not much different in total number indicating that the properties of the soils associated with functional group of these two regions are fairly well stabilized than those associated with the functional groups indicated by peaks between 8.50μ to 10.30μ .

The characteristic IR-absorption peaks of semi-arid, sub-humid, humid-temperate and per-humid soils comprising 14, 8, 6 and 2 soils respectively have been shown in table 1. In general, these soils show greater number of peaks, greater sharpness and greater differentiation of peaks as compared to semi-desert and arid soils which are said to have more capacity to produce successfully greater variety of crops². It may be observed that among those peaks there are some common one which may perhaps be useful in the identification of these soils. The peak values (Table 1) in different infra-red regions of IR-curves of semi-arid, sub-humid, humid and per-humid regions are as follows :

Semi-arid : 2.95μ , 6.10μ , 9.10μ , 9.75μ , 12.50μ and 14.45μ

Sub-humid : 2.80μ , 3.50μ , 6.15μ , 9.0μ , 11.0μ , 12.50μ , and 14.45μ

Humid-temperate : 2.95μ , 9.10μ , 9.70μ and 12.50μ

Per humid : 6.15μ , 7.35μ , 8.10μ , 9.10μ , 10.0μ , 10.95μ , 12.50μ , 12.75μ and 14.45μ .

These common peak values for a particular functional group observed in a particular soil-climatic region-soils may be very useful for making their detail study especially in relation to the nature of bond of their constituting atoms. The other peak values for different functional groups would obviously be characteristic for a particular soil belonging to the same soil-climatic region and would therefore be more variable than the common peak values mentioned earlier due to the operation of some local factors.

In table 3, it may be observed that the total IR-peaks in the region of IR-curves of 8.50μ to 10.30μ and 11.0μ to 15.0μ are not much different in all the soils of semi-arid, sub-humid, humid-temperate and per-humid regions but this is not so far as the number of peaks shown under 2.70μ to 8.0μ and total number of strong peaks are concerned. Thus the soil properties associated with the functional groups observed at 8.50μ to 10.30μ and 11.0μ to 15.0μ have become more stabilized so as to give some common characteristics to peaks for all the soils of semi-desert, sub-humid, humid-temperate and per-humid soil-climatic regions, obviously this is not so for the properties associated with the functional group at 2.70μ to 8.0μ . The variation on total number of peaks in all the soil climatic regions is obviously more due to the functional group denoting the peak values between 2.70μ to 8.0μ . The total number of peaks (average) in semi-arid, sub-humid, humid-temperate and per-humid regions are found to be 11, 12, 12, and 14 respectively, which are said to be generally higher than either the semi-desert or arid soils (10 or 11) and therefore depending upon De's² conclusions, it may be said that these soils have greater capacity to grow successfully greater variety of crops than either semi-desert or arid soils.

It may be pointed out that De² reported the region for Si-H (E) bond between 11.0μ to 11.20μ but in our case the IR-peak values for Si-H (E) bond have been obtained at 10.95μ by semi-arid soils (6 soils), humid-temperate soils (2 soils) and per-humid soils (2 soils) and for semi-arid (8 soils), sub-humid (8 soils) and humid-temperate (4 soils) soil climatic regions-soils this peak has been found at 11.0μ (Table 2).

In the end, it may be pointed out that De² reported that when in the IR curves of soils the total number of peaks are more than six, the soils are useful from the point of view of crop productivity because the latter depends on certain soil properties such as higher b.a.c. which is well reflected in their IR-curves by recording higher number of peaks.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (Sharafat Ali) is thankful to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi for financial assistance.

References

1. R. J. DYER, Application of Absorption Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds, Prentice-Hall of India, Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, 1965.
2. S. K. DE, D.Sc. Thesis, University of Allahabad, Allahabad, 1965.
3. S. K. DE, *Indian J. Agril. Chem.*, 1968, 1(1), 12.
4. U. SCHIEDT, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1952, 76, 270.
5. S. LAL, D.Sc. Thesis, University of Allahabad, Allahabad, 1973.
6. GULAB SINGH, D.Sc., University of Allahabad, Allahabad, 1970.
7. R. LANGS, *Intern. Mitt. Bodenkund.* 1915, 5, 312.
8. S. K. DE, Methods of Soil Analysis, Narayan Publishing House, Allahabad, 1962.